

TRIGONOMETRIK TENGLAMALARNI YECHISH USULLARI HAQIDA

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Toshkent shahar Yakkasaroy tumani 26-maktabning matematika fani o'qituvchisi

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada trigonometrik tenglamalarni yechish usullari haqida ma'lumotlar berilgan. Trigonometrik tenglamalar haqida tushunchalar keltirilgan va misollar yechish orqali tahlilqilingan.

Kalit so'zlar: Trigonometriya, funksiyaning chegaralanganlik xossasi, proporsiya.

О СПОСОБАХ РЕШЕНИЯ ТРИГОНОМЕТРИЧЕСКИХ УРАВНЕНИЙ

Аннотация. В этой статье представлена информация о методах решения тригонометрических уравнений. Даны понятия о тригонометрических уравнениях и проанализированы на примерах решения.

Ключевые слова: тригонометрия, свойство предела функции, пропорция.

ABOUT METHODS FOR SOLVING TRIGONOMETRIC EQUATIONS

Abstract. This article provides information on methods for solving trigonometric equations. Concepts about trigonometric equations are presented and analyzed by solving examples.

Keywords: trigonometry, function delimitation property, proportion.

Uzluksiz ta'limning barcha bosqichlaridagi o'quvchi va talabalarni teran fikrlovchi bilimli va mantiqiy xulosa chiqara oluvchi sifatida tarbiyalash bugungi kunda ta'lim beruvchilar oldidagi eng muhim vazifa hisoblanadi. Kelajak uchun har tomonlama yetuk mutaxassis kadrlar tayyorlashning mohiyati, zaruriyati, zamonaviy fan va texnikaning rivojlanish talablariga mos barkamol avlodni tarbiyalash masalalarini izchillik bilan tashkil etish, bu boradagi dolzarb masalalar va ularni amalga oshirish chora tadbiri milliy dasturda belgilab berilgan. Shu ma'noda trigonometrik tengsizliklarni o'rganishning innavatsion usulini misol tariqasida keltirishni lozim topdik. Ma'lumki, trigonometriya matematikaning muhim bo'limlaridan biri hisoblanib, geometriya va astronomiya fanlarining ham asosi hisoblanadi.

“Trigonometriya” atamasi grekcha “trigono” - uchburchak va “metrio” – o'lchayman so'zlaridan olingan bo'lib, birgalikda “uchburchakni o'lchash” ma'nosini anglatadi.

O'quvchilar eng sodda trigonometrik tenglamalar va tengsizliklarni yecha oladilar; tenglamalar va tengsizliklar va ularning sistemalarini yechadi, yechimini tekshiradi.

Trigonometrik tenglamalarni ko'rinishiga qarab yechishning bir qancha usullari mavjud. Bularga o'rniga qo'yish, ratsionallashtiradigan o'rniga qo'yishlar, trigonometrik tenglamalarni yechishning har xil xususiy hollari, sun'iy shakl almashtirishlardan foydalanib trigonometrik tenglamalarni yechish va hokazo. Ba'zi hollarda berilgan tenglamalarni biz bilgan usullar bilan yechish ancha murakkab bo'ladi. Bunday tenglamalarni yechishning nostandart

usullariga to'xtab o'tamiz. Sun'iy shakl almashtirish talab qiladigan trigonometrik tenglamalarni yechishda quyidagi usullardan foydalaniladi.

I. Tenglamani har ikki tomonini bir hil trigonometrik funksiyaga ko'paytirish.

1-misol. $2\cos x(2\cos 4x+1)=1$ tenglamani yeching.

Yechish: Qavslarni ochib, $4\cos 4x\cos x+2\cos x=1$ ni, $\cos 4x \cdot \cos x$ ko'paytmani shakl almashtirib

$$2\cos 5x+2\cos 3x+2\cos x=1$$

ni hosil qilamiz.

Tenglamani har 2 tomonini $\sin x$ ga ko'paytiramiz.

$$x=\pi n, \quad n \in \mathbb{Z}$$

tenglamani yechimi bo'lmasligini ko'ramiz.

$$2\sin x\cos 5x+2\sin x\cos 3x+2\cos x\sin x=\sin x.$$

Tenglamani chap tomonida turgan ko'paytmani shakl almashtiramiz.

$$\sin 6x - \sin 4x + \sin 4x - \sin 2x + \sin 2x = \sin x;$$

$$\sin 6x = \sin x$$

$$2\sin \frac{5x}{2} \cos \frac{7x}{2} = 0.$$

Bundan $2\sin \frac{5x}{2} = 0$ yoki $\cos \frac{7x}{2} = 0$.

Bu tenglamalardan $x = \frac{2\pi k}{5}; \quad k \in \mathbb{Z}.$

$$x = \frac{\pi}{7} + \frac{2\pi m}{7}, \quad m \in \mathbb{Z}.$$

Bu ildizlar orasidan $x = \pi n, \quad n \in \mathbb{Z}$ ko'rinishdagi ildizlarni chiqarib tashlaymiz.

a) $\frac{2\pi k}{5} \neq \pi n, \quad n \in \mathbb{Z}, \quad k \neq \frac{5n}{2}; \quad n \in \mathbb{Z}.$ $n =$ juft son ekanligi ma'lum.

$n = 2l, \quad l \in \mathbb{Z}.$ Shuning uchun $k \neq 5l, \quad l \in \mathbb{Z}.$

b) $\frac{\pi(1+2m)}{7} \neq \pi n, \quad n \in \mathbb{Z}, \quad m \neq \frac{7n-1}{2}, \quad n \in \mathbb{Z}$

$m \in \mathbb{Z}$ bo'lgani uchun $n \neq 2p+1, \quad p \in \mathbb{Z},$ u holda $m \neq 7p+3, \quad p \in \mathbb{Z}$

Javob: $\frac{2\pi k}{5}, \quad k \in \mathbb{Z}, \quad k \neq 5l, \quad l \in \mathbb{Z}$

$\frac{\pi(1+2m)}{7}; \quad m \in \mathbb{Z}, \quad m \neq 7p+3, \quad p \in \mathbb{Z}.$

II. Tenglamani har 2 tomoniga bir hil son yoki bir hil trigonometrik funksiyani qo'shish.

2-misol. $\operatorname{tg} x \cdot \operatorname{tg} 2x = \operatorname{tg} 3x \cdot \operatorname{tg} 4x$ tenglamani yeching.

Yechish: Tenglamani aniqlanish sohasi

$$x \neq \frac{\pi}{2} + \pi n, \quad x \neq \frac{\pi}{4} + \frac{\pi n}{2}; \quad x \neq \frac{\pi}{6} + \frac{\pi n}{3}; \quad x \neq \frac{\pi}{8} + \frac{\pi n}{4}; \quad n \in \mathbb{Z}$$

Tenglamani har 2 tomoniga 1 ni qo'shamiz.

$$\operatorname{tg} x \operatorname{tg} 2x + 1 = \operatorname{tg} 3x \operatorname{tg} 4x + 1.$$

$$\frac{\cos x}{\cos x \cos 2x} = \frac{\cos x}{\cos 3x \cos 4x}.$$

tenglamani har 2 tomonini $\cos x \neq 0$ ga bo'lamiz.

$$\cos x + \cos 3x = \cos 7x + \cos x$$

$$\cos 7x - \cos 3x = 0$$

$\sin 2x \sin 5x = 0;$ u holda $x = \frac{\pi}{2} k, \quad k \in \mathbb{Z}$ yoki

$$x = \frac{\pi}{5} t, \quad t \in \mathbb{Z}.$$

Birinchi ildizlar to'plamidan tenglamani aniqlanish sohasiga faqat $x = \pi m, \quad m \in \mathbb{Z}$

$$\frac{\pi}{5}$$

tegishli, ammo bu ildizlar to'plami $x = \frac{\pi}{5}t, t \in Z$ da mavjud.

$x = \frac{\pi}{5}t; t \in Z$ tenglamaning aniqlanish sohasiga tegishli ekanligini ko'rish qiyin emas.

Masalan,

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\pi}{5}t &\neq \frac{\pi}{4} + \frac{\pi n}{2}, \\ 4t &\neq 5 + 10n; \\ 4t \square 10n &\neq 5. \end{aligned}$$

Oxirgi tenglikning chap qismi juft, o'ng qismi toq sonidir.

$$\text{Javob: } x = \frac{\pi}{5}t; t \in Z.$$

III. Tenglamaning biror bir qismini ayniy shakl almashtirish. (Bir xil ifodani qo'shish yoki ayirish).

3-misol. $\cos 7x = \cos^3 x$ tenglamani yeching.

Yechish: Tenglamaning chap qismini shakl almashtiramiz.

$$(\cos 7x \square \cos 5x) + (\cos 5x \square \cos 3x) + (\cos 3x \square \cos x) + \cos x = \cos^3 x;$$

$$\square 2 \sin 6x \sin x \square 2 \sin 4x \sin x \square 2 \sin 2x \sin x + \cos x = \cos^3 x;$$

$$\square 2 \sin x (\sin 6x + \sin 4x + \sin 2x) = \cos x (\cos^2 x \square 1);$$

$$\square 2 \sin x (2 \sin 4x \cos 2x + \sin 4x) + \sin^2 x \cos x = 0;$$

$$8 \sin^2 x \cos x \cos 2x (2 \cos 2x + 1) \square \sin^2 x \cos x = 0;$$

bundan

$$\sin^2 x \cos x = 0,$$

u holda

$$x = \frac{\pi}{2}n, n \in Z$$

yoki

$$8 \cos 2x (2 \cos 2x + 1) \square 1 = 0.$$

$$16 \cos^2 2x + 8 \cos 2x \square 1 = 0.$$

$$\cos 2x = \frac{\square 1 \pm \sqrt{2}}{4}; x = \pm \frac{1}{2} \arccos \frac{\square 1 \pm \sqrt{2}}{4} + \pi k, k \in Z.$$

$$\text{Javob: } \frac{\pi}{2}n, n \in Z, \pm \frac{1}{2} \arccos \frac{\square 1 \pm \sqrt{2}}{4} + \pi k; k \in Z.$$

IV. $\frac{a}{b} = \frac{c}{d}$ proporsiyadan foydalanish.

$$\frac{a+b}{a \square b} = \frac{c+d}{c \square d}; \frac{a \square b}{a+b} = \frac{c \square d}{c+d}; \frac{a \square c}{b \square d} = \frac{a}{b}; \frac{a}{b} = \frac{a+c}{b+d}.$$

Bu tengliklardan foydalanish tenglamaning aniqlanish sohasining kengayishiga olib keladi.

Agar $\frac{a}{b} = \frac{c}{d} (b \neq 0; d \neq 0)$ bo'lsa, $\frac{a \square b}{a+b} = \frac{c \square d}{c+d}$; bunda $a \neq \square b$ va $c \neq \square d$.

4-misol. $\frac{2\sqrt{3} \cos 10^0 + 1}{2 \sin 10^0 + 1} = \frac{\text{tg} 3x}{\text{tg} x}$ tenglamani yeching.

Yechish: Tenglamaning aniqlanish sohasi $\cos 3x \neq 0, \cos x \neq 0, \sin x \neq 0$ tengsizliklar bilan aniqlanadi.

Proporsiya xossasiga ko'ra

$$\frac{2\sqrt{3} \cos 10^0 + 2 \sin 10^0 + 2}{2\sqrt{3} \cos 10^0 \square 2 \sin 10^0} = \frac{\text{tg} 3x + \text{tg} x}{\text{tg} 3x \square \text{tg} x}$$

$$\frac{\sqrt{3 \cos 10^\circ + \sin 10^\circ} + 1}{\sqrt{\sin 4x}} = \frac{\sin 4x}{3 \cos 10^\circ} \square \frac{\sin 10^\circ}{\sin 2x}$$

$$\frac{2 \cos 20^\circ + 1}{2 \cos 40^\circ} = 2 \cos 2x; \quad \frac{\cos 20^\circ + \cos 60^\circ}{\cos 40^\circ \cos 2x} = 2 \cos 2x;$$

$$\cos 40^\circ \cos 2x = \cos 20^\circ.$$

$$x = \pm 10^\circ \pm 180^\circ n; \quad n \in \mathbb{Z}.$$

Javob: $\pm 10^\circ + 180^\circ n;$

$n \in \mathbb{Z}.$

Trigonometrik tenglamalarni yechishda matematik tahlil elementlaridan foydalanish.

I. Funksiyaning aniqlanish sohasidan foydalanish.

Ba'zi hollarda tenglamaning aniqlanish sohasini bilish tenglamaning ildizi yo'qligini isbotlashni, ba'zida esa tenglamaning yechimini aniqlanish sohasidan son qo'yib ko'rib topishni taqozo qiladi.

1-misol. $\sqrt{|\sin x|} = \sqrt[4]{|\sin x|} + \operatorname{tg} x$ (1) tenglamani yeching.

Yechish. Tenglamaning aniqlanish sohasi

$$\begin{cases} |\sin x| \geq 0 \\ \sqrt[4]{|\sin x|} \geq 0 \\ x \neq \frac{\pi}{2} + \pi n; \quad n \in \mathbb{Z} \end{cases}$$

dan iborat. Bundan $x = \pi k$, $k \in \mathbb{Z}$. x ning bu qiymatini (1) tenglamaga qo'yib uning o'ng va chap tomonlari 0 ga tengligini ko'ramiz. Demak, hamma $x = \pi k$; $k \in \mathbb{Z}$ lar tenglamaning ildizi bo'lar ekan.

J: $x = \pi k$; $k \in \mathbb{Z}.$

II. Funksiyaning chegaralanganlik xossasidan foydalanish.

Tenglamalarni yechishda funksiyaning biror to'plamda quyidan yoki yuqoridan chegaralanganligi xossasi ko'p hollarda katta rol o'ynaydi. Masalan, biror M to'plamdagi barcha x lar uchun $f(x) > A$ va $g(x) < A$ (A biror son) tengsizliklar o'rinli bo'lsa, u holda M to'plamda $f(x) = g(x)$ tenglama yechimga ega emas.

A soni o'rnida ko'p hollarda nol bo'ladi, bu esa $f(x)$ va $g(x)$ funksiyalarning M to'plamda ishorasi saqlanishini bildiradi.

2-misol. $\sin(x^3 + 2x^2 + 1) = x^2 + 2x + 3$ tenglamani yeching.

Yechish: Ixtiyoriy x haqiqiy soni uchun $\sin(x^3 + 2x^2 + 1) \leq 1$. $x^2 + 2x + 3 = (x+1)^2 + 2 \geq 2$. Bundan esa ixtiyoriy x haqiqiy soni uchun tenglamaning chap tomoni 1 dan oshmaydi, o'ng tomoni har doim 2 dan kichik emasligini ko'ramiz. Demak, tenglamaning yechimi yo'q ekan.

J: \emptyset .

3-misol. $2 \sin x = 5x^2 + 2x + 3$ tenglamani yeching.

Yechish: Ma'lumki, $y = 5x^2 + 2x + 3$ funksiyaning grafigi $y = 2 \sin x$ funksiyaning grafigidan yuqorida yotadi. U holda $5x^2 + 2x + 3 > 2 \sin x$

Javob: \emptyset .

Ushbu maqolada trigonometrik tenglamalarning yechimidan innovatsion foydalanib ishlash. Bu o'quvchilarda trigonometriyaga va umuman olganda, matematikaga qiziqishini oshiradi, degan xulosaga kelish mumkin.

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